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Considerations about a Methodological Approach for Multi-service and Multi-priority Traffic Parameters Optimization

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Abstract — This paper proposes a simple methodological approach to represent quality of service parameters in multi-service and multi-priority networks and discusses the identification of methods and dependencies to handle network parameters targeting an optimization method. Both the approach to represent network parameters and the optimization methods are part of a more general framework intended to optimize resource allocation in DiffServ domains.

In general terms, frameworks dealing with the provisioning of IP networks may be classified as both static and dynamic. Static frameworks are much more common since implementation, although requiring a global knowledge of the network node states, is simplified with resources provisioning being typically evaluated by a tool in out-of-band style. Dynamic frameworks for router provisioning have a more delicate balance to deal with. In particular, the required operation timing may represent a huge constraint in terms of network responsiveness to both acquire network state and processing in order to optimize network resources.

I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Routing in IP networks (internet and enterprise networks) was originally conceived to address connectivity supporting only best effort style of traffic. Multimedia applications are currently a trend in IP networks and, as such, quality of service (QoS) guarantees becomes an important requirement [Martins, 1999] [Martins, 2002].

When quality of service is considered for routing, paths for specific flows and aggregates are typically selected based on knowledge about resource availability and QoS requirements with respect to the selected path. DiffServ [Blake, 1998] and MPLS [Awduche, 1999] [Aidarous 2003], among others, are examples of technical alternatives to handle path selection and QoS guarantees to multimedia applications in general. These solutions assume to a certain extent that resources (link capacity, buffers, scheduling algorithms, other) have been somehow provisioned at network level and, routing decisions are typically based on a defined network scenario for routers (nodes) and other backbone equipments.

When considering router provisioning methods and techniques, technical alternatives have recently been proposed to the problem [Saad, 2002] [Saad, 2001].

Considering this scenario, our proposal first suggests the need for a clear methodological approach to represent the variety of traffic flows and aggregates in current multiservice and multipriority IP networks. The proposed approach is intended to approximate actual network dimensioning scenario and, as such, it is assumed that acquired knowledge will consist basically of link capacity and topology information. Also, we assume that parameter estimation might be carried out by the selection of mathematical tools derived from identification of traffic sources characteristics and network parameters dependencies. Finally, it is considered that resource provisioning in IP nodes may make use of either classical static provisioning or may use a dynamic solution.

Network flow theory itself requires methods from graph theory, combinatorial mathematics, optimization theory, mathematical programming, and heuristic programming [Kleinrock, 1975]. In general terms, we suggest that an engineering approach based on a set of currently known solutions might be helpful in approaching the QoS provisioning optimization problem [Brito 2002a].

II. MODELLING FLOWS AND AGGREGATES

The traffic model proposed suits any DiffServ domain scenario where service classes accommodate traffic flows and aggregates through the network.

The proposed simple model considers, as conventional, a network with sources, nodes, direct links and sinks and is intended to easier simulates the behavior of specific flow or aggregate in, for instance, a DiffServ domain (Fig. 01).

Figure 01 – Basic flow representation

Sources (S_i) represent any type of multimedia traffic generated by a particular user. In terms of this model, a source represents a generated flow (F_i), corresponding to a set of packets from a specific external user or identifiable port and machine at the network. In a more general perspective, external applications or external users may be represented as a set of sources and sinks corresponding to the multiple media flows passing throughout the network in both directions. In this way, a flow is conventionally identifiable by the port and IP addresses at both sides of the network, corresponding to the exchange of simplex or full-duplex media between two network users (applications). This suitable choice allows a more precise representation of traffic characteristics with respect to individual flows and aggregates in nodes. Also, this style of representation allows a more precise identification of network characteristics for both multimedia simplex traffic and full-duplex asymmetric traffic, typical in conventional data applications inside the network. Then, following a simulation model scheme, packets flow from source to sink through a certain number of nodes. Application or external user behavior may be

represented by a set of specific flows in both directions.

The node (N_i), in simple terms, has an internal structure composed of a packet forwarding decision point associated with the packet's final destination (Fig. 02). In other words, packets are forwarded to specific output links. A set of service classes (S_i) is associated with each link (L_i) with the flows belonging to a specific service class. Also, flows may be assembled in aggregates (A_i) to have a more common treatment in nodes. Finally, a scheduling algorithm is associated to each output queue to share the link capacity among the various flows and aggregates. For simplicity, we assume that other functionalities typically present in edge nodes such as shaping, marking, and policing are less relevant to parameters estimation in core or internal nodes.

Figure 02 – Basic node representation

Flows, aggregates and nodes have both a topological representation and descriptive parameters behavior. The parameters considered to represent domain behavior are:

Packet arrival rate (λ), queue service capacity (C) and queue buffer length (l).

In terms of behavior measures for the network the following parameters may be considered:

Delay (D), jitter (J), packet loss (L) and utilization (ρ).

It follows a specific example that shows how a more concise representation of the system behavior may be achieved by using the simplified model proposed.

III. CONSIDERATIONS ABOUT PARAMETER OPTIMIZATION APPROACHES

The optimization of network node resources is a challenging research topic [Brownlee, 2002] [Fortz, 2002]. In our approach, to optimize parameters

during network operation, we initially suggest that a framework consisting of acquisition, processing and actuation elements, with various implementation alternatives is necessary. Due to the complexity of the problem, the framework may assume different approaches in both provisioning the nodes and acquiring relevant data for processing [Brito, 2002].

One basic approach to adequate network behavior, in terms of quality of service parameters with respect to the offered load, is to assume an explicit limitation of the load offered to the network by controlling the traffic contracts and policing traffic at network edge. This is a common practice used in many network operators and private backbones.

A second approach to control network behavior consists in using optimization methods for specific network parameters in order to adjust the global network operation with respect to the offered load. In this approach, a methodological model for parameters and behavior representation is necessary and, as such, we argue that part of the complexity involved in relating flows and aggregate's behavior can be better observed and, as such, optimizations methods decisions may be easily achieved.

When considering specifically the optimization problem in DiffServ domains, an optimization model called proportional differentiation is proposed in [Dovrolis, 2002]. In this model, a relational proportion regulates capacity by class as such that, loss and delay for a class remain in a specified range independently from the offered load. The end-to-end optimization problem is also analyzed in [Dovrolis, 2001] using the proportional differentiation model.

IV. OPTMIZATION APPROACH BY USING THE UTILIZATION PARAMETER

Utilization (ρ) is one of the possible parameters that might be used to optimize network resources [Brito, 2002]. Utilization is interpreted as the percentage relation between used and available resources in a given instant for an individual queue or, more generically, for a node. Utilization provides in effect an effective way to complement traffic contracts and policing mechanisms in order to adjust network nodes with respect to traffic variation. One basic principle adopted in this solution is such that by adjusting the allocated capacities for each class in a DiffServ domain other quality of service parameters can be adjusted and effectively brought to expected levels of performance [Brito, 2002].

Figure 03 – Network scenario

The network scenario considered is the one illustrated in figure 03. All paths available between nodes 1 and 3 for this specific topology are represented in table 01:

Table 01: Paths between nodes 1 and 3 in the domain

Source – Sink	1-3	
	A	B
L _{1,2}	1	
L _{1,3}		1
L _{2,3}	2	

According with table 01, packets paths between nodes 1 and 3 have two alternatives “A” and “B”. Each element of the table indicates that the link belongs to the path and, besides that, the sequence when walking on the path. As an example, path “A” uses links L_{1,2} and L_{2,3} in sequence.

Utilization is expressed as follows:

$$\rho = \frac{\lambda}{C} \quad (1)$$

For the traffic aggregates considered, it is assumed that both traffic arrival and queue servicing are markovian processes. Based on [Kleinrock, 1975] the system delay by class and by node is as follows:

$$D_{S, Ns, Nd, P} = \frac{1}{C_{S, Ns, Nd} - \lambda_{S, Ns, Nd}} \quad (2)$$

where:

- C – service capacity for class S
- λ – aggregate arrival rate for class S
- P – path
- Ns – source node
- Nd – end node

From (1) and (2) the delay function for the path "A" for classes 1 and 2 is as follows:

$$D_{1,1,3,A} = \frac{1}{c_{1,1,2} - \lambda_{1,1,2}} + \frac{1}{c_{1,2,3} - \lambda_{1,2,3}} \quad (3)$$

$$D_{2,1,3,A} = \frac{1}{c_{2,1,2} - \lambda_{2,1,2}} + \frac{1}{c_{2,2,3} - \lambda_{2,2,3}} \quad (4)$$

The utilization by class and by node may then be described as follows:

Class 1 at node 01:

$$\rho_{1,1,2} = \frac{\lambda_{1,1,2}}{c_{1,1,2}} \quad (5)$$

Class 1 at node 02:

$$\rho_{1,2,3} = \frac{\lambda_{1,2,3}}{c_{1,2,3}} \quad (6)$$

Class 2 at node 1:

$$\rho_{2,1,2} = \frac{\lambda_{2,1,2}}{c_{2,1,2}} \quad (7)$$

Class 2 at node 2:

$$\rho_{2,2,3} = \frac{\lambda_{2,2,3}}{c_{2,2,3}} \quad (8)$$

For path "B" the following results may be deduced in terms of the delay:

$$D_{1,1,3,B} = \frac{1}{c_{1,1,3} - \lambda_{1,1,3}} \quad (9)$$

For the path "B" the utilization per class and per node is as follows:

Class 1 at node 1:

$$\rho_{1,1,3} = \frac{\lambda_{1,1,3}}{c_{1,1,3}} \quad (10)$$

Class 2 at node 1:

$$\rho_{2,1,3} = \frac{\lambda_{2,1,3}}{c_{2,1,3}}$$

The simple and methodological representation proposed allows two different conclusions for the

specific problem of using utilization as a regulation parameter for global optimization in DiffServ networks:

a. the successive quadratic programming (SQP) algorithm may be used; and

b. system optimization may be visualized by identifying and defining contour conditions for parameters by node, link or specific service.

In effect, the objective function and constraints comprise a nonlinear programming problem and can be solved using the Successive Quadratic Programming (SQP) algorithm [Bazarra, 1993] also applied in control problems [Henson, 1998]. Loosely speaking, this method linearizes inequality and equality constraints and constructs a convex quadratic objective function from gradients of the objective and constraints functions. The resulting quadratic program (QP) can be solved using any standard, finite-step QP algorithm. Hence, the basic step in the SQP algorithm is the formulation and solution of the quadratic programming problem.

As far as the parameter optimization inspection method is concerned it can be easily verified for equation (9) that the delay may be considered a restriction condition and, besides that, its dependencies with respect to link and service classes are established. By using equation (10) variations on the aggregate changes the utilization and have an intrinsic impact on the delay. Being so, by adjusting the utilization through regulation of allocated capacities, an expected delay may be achieved. It is important to emphasize that dependencies on link, node and service are clearly visualized by using the methodological representation proposed.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper argues that a methodological approach to represent flows and aggregates in complex networks might be useful. Once the network topology, flows and aggregates are modeled, the identification of both the optimization method and parameters dependencies and relationship are more easily identifiable. By using the methodology, it is expected that part of the difficulty in handling large and complex networks in order to provision and collect data for quality of service optimization is reduced allowing thus an engineering-like approach as part of the network optimization problem solution.

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